

One pot synthesis of monodisperse water soluble iron oxide nanocrystals with high values of specific absorption rate

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ABSTRACT: We report a highly reproducible route to synthesize iron oxide nanoparticles (IONPs) with control over size and shape and with size dispersions around 10%. By tuning the relative ratio of squalane to dibenzyl ether, which were used as solvents in the synthesis, the size of the particles could be varied from 14 to around 100 nm, while their shape evolved from cubic (for size ranges up to 35 nm) to truncated octahedra and octahedra (for sizes from 40 nm up to 100 nm). Fine tuning of the size within each of these

ranges could be achieved by varying the heating ramp and the iron precursor to decanoic acid ratio. We also demonstrate direct water transfer of the as-synthesized IONPs *via in situ* ligand exchange with gallol polyethylene glycol molecules, the latter simply added to the crude nanocrystal mixture at 70°C. The specific absorption rate (SAR) values measured on the water transferred IONPs, at frequencies and applied magnetic fields that are considered safe for patients, confirmed their high heating performance. Finally, this method allows the transfer of 35 nm nanocubes as individually coated and stable particles into water. For the first time, the heating performance of such large IONPs has been studied. This work uncovers the possibility to use large IONPs for magnetic hyperthermia in tumor therapy.

KEYWORDS: Iron oxide nanocubes, magnetic nanoparticles, biomedical applications, hyperthermia treatment, SAR values

Introduction

Magnetic hyperthermia, in alternative or in combination with radio- and chemotherapy, has been proposed as a novel cancer treatment.¹⁻² In this approach, a local temperature increase is triggered by the interaction of magnetic nanoparticles with an alternating magnetic field (AMF) at the site of accumulation. The heat generated can selectively kill tumour cells, as they are more vulnerable than healthy cells to stress induced by elevated temperatures.³⁻⁵ One important figure of merit in hyperthermia is the so-called specific absorption rate (SAR), which provides a measure of the heat performance of the magnetic nanoparticles.⁶⁻⁷ Various types of nanoparticles have been proposed as efficient heat mediators: among them, iron-based materials, and more precisely iron oxide nanoparticles (IONPs), are the most promising ones. Many studies on spherical nanoparticles have been published to date and attempts have been made to synthesize large particles.^{8-10 11} It was found however that, when the size of these spherical NCs was above 15 nm, their magnetic (and heating) performance started degrading. On the other hand, cubic-shaped IONPs with sizes above 15 nm have shown the highest SAR values reported so far,⁴ in line with the SAR values of magnetosomes, which are cubic-shaped IONPs synthesized by magnetotactic bacteria.¹² This has been

demonstrated both for individually dispersed nanocubes⁴ and for small clusters of nanocubes.¹³ In addition, these nanocubes exhibit short T2 relaxation times which make them promising contrast agents for *in vivo* magnetic resonance imaging.¹⁴⁻¹⁵ Finally, their magnetic properties, high biocompatibility and degradability *in vivo* via a well-defined degradation pathway make iron oxide nanocubes probably the best heat mediators thus far available for clinical applications.^{4, 16-17} For most *in vivo* applications, uniform nanoparticles, in terms of both size and shape distributions, are required.¹⁸⁻²⁰ Size and shape distributions affect critically both nanoparticle surface chemistry and magnetic properties and hence colloidal stability and SAR values of the resulting nanoparticles.^{9, 21-24}

In comparison to the many non-hydrolytic synthesis approaches to spherical IONPs, fewer synthetic studies have been published on cubic IONPs.^{8, 11, 25-26} Most of these works list dibenzyl ether (DBE) as one of the chemicals involved in the synthesis, suggesting that, if one wants to prepare large cubes (for example larger than 15 nm, where large SAR values are observed), this compound must be present in the reaction environment.^{4, 14-15, 27-30} Unfortunately, repeated tests in our laboratories have indicated that the use of DBE as solvent results in poor reproducibility, which led us to investigate in detail the role of this/it in the synthesis of cubic IONPs. We found that, the temperature fluctuations arising from the decomposition of DBE and the formation of the decomposition molecules represent the main cause of poor reproducibility in the synthesis (Figure 1a). We then found that a much higher reproducibility can be achieved by adding squalane to the reaction mixture. The addition of this solvent, characterized by a high boiling point, helps to smooth temperature fluctuations and enables the synthesis of nanocrystals over a wide range of sizes, by simply adjusting the ratio of squalane to DBE. On one hand the presence of DBE is fundamental for controlling the shape and the size of the nanocrystals, since its decomposition at refluxing conditions generates molecules that take an active role in controlling the nucleation and the size of the nanocubes. With such modified procedure, particles with well-defined cubic shapes were synthesized in the range between 14 and 35 nm, and with octahedral or truncated octahedral shapes in the range from 40 nm up to 100 nm. Once the ratio of squalane to DBE had been set, a fine tuning of the

particle size was then possible by variation of either the heating ramp or the ratio of the iron precursor to decanoic acid.

We additionally report a new protocol to directly transfer the as synthesized nanocubes in water. Even if several approaches have been previously developed in this direction,^{5,31} the quantitative water transfer of nanoparticles as individually coated crystals becomes challenging when the particles are at the limit between the superparamagnetic and the ferromagnetic regime at room temperature. This is the case of cubic shaped IONPs with sizes above 15 nm, which are characterized by strong magnetic dipole-dipole interactions. We achieved a nearly quantitative (90% yield) water transfer of our iron oxide nanocubes, by adding gallol polyethylene glycol (GA-PEG) in the last step of the synthesis, *i.e.* to the crude nanocrystal solution, once the temperature had been lowered from refluxing temperature to 70 °C. The water transferred nanoparticles, with sizes ranging from 14 ± 1.5 nm up to 35 ± 2 nm, were all characterized by high SAR values. The here reported *in situ* ligand exchange protocol results in a high colloidal stability for cubic IONPs with sizes up to 35 nm in water. This allows, for the first time, to measure the SAR values of colloidal, not agglomerated, cubic IONPs with sizes up to 35 nm in aqueous media.

Experimental Methods

Materials. Iron (III) acetylacetonate (99%), decanoic acid (99%) and dibenzyl ether (99%) were purchased from Acros. Squalane (98%) was purchased from Alfa Aesar. Benzyl alcohol (99%), Gallic acid, Poly(ethylene glycol) (1500 g/mol), N,N'-Dicyclohexylcarbodiimide, 4-Dimethylaminopyridine and all solvents were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Milli-Q water (18.2 M Ω , filtered with filter pore size 0.22 μ M) was from Millipore. All solvents used were of analytical grade and were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. All chemicals were used as received.

Synthesis of iron oxide nanocubes by tuning the dibenzyl ether / squalane ratio. All experiments were carried out in 50 mL (14/23) three neck round bottom flasks equipped with a water cooled Allihn-condensers connected to a standard Schlenk line. The following conditions were the most suitable for

synthesizing cubes of different sizes. Details are reported here only for the synthesis of the 100 nm particles. Conditions for preparing all the particle sizes discussed in this work are summarized in Table S1. Briefly, in a 50 mL three neck flask, 0.353 g (1 mmol) of iron (III) acetylacetonate with 0.69 g (4 mmols) of decanoic acid and 3 mL of dibenzyl ether (DBE) were dissolved in 22 mL of squalane. After degassing for 120 minutes at 65 °C, the mixture was heated up to 200 °C (3 °C/min) and kept at this value for 2.5 h (a shorter “ageing time” at 200 °C led to a lower reproducibility as well as to a broadening of the size and shape distributions of the final particles). The temperature was then increased at a heating rate of 7 °C/min up to 310 °C or reflux temperature and maintained at this value for 1 h (Figure 2A). After cooling down to room temperature, 60 mL of acetone were added and the solution was centrifuged at 8500 rpm. The supernatant was then discarded and the black precipitate was dispersed in 2-3 mL of chloroform: this washing procedure was repeated at least two more times. Finally the collected particles were dispersed in 15 mL of chloroform. By changing the ratio between DBE and squalane and keeping the other parameters constant, smaller particles can be synthesized. For instance; 38 ± 4 nm, 26 ± 3 nm, 21 ± 2 nm and 14 ± 2 nm nanocubes were synthesized by using 21 mL of squalane and 4 mL of DBE, 18 mL of squalane and 7 mL of DBE, 16 mL of squalane and 9 mL of DBE and 23 mL of DBE and 2 mL of squalane, respectively (Figure 2 and Figure S1). It is also worth to underline the importance of the vacuum step as we found the system to be very sensitive to moisture/air. In all the syntheses we applied vacuum for 120 minutes at 0.1 mbar and at a temperature of 65 °C.

Transfer of iron oxide nanocrystals into polar solvents. The synthesis of Gallic Acid PEG ligand is reported in the Electronic Supporting Information (ESI). For the transfer of IONPs into polar solvent; briefly, after reducing the temperature of the reaction mixture from 310 to 70°C, 15 mL GA-PEG solution (0.1M in chloroform containing 1 mL triethylamine) were injected and stirred over night at constant temperature. The mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature and transferred in a separating funnel. 10 mL of de-ionized water were added resulting in two phases. After emulsification by means of shaking, the phases were allowed to separate and the aqueous phase containing the IONPs bearing GA-PEG collected. This step was repeated until all nanocubes were transferred into water. After concentration

under reduced pressure at 40°C to a final volume of circa 50 mL, the excess of GA-PEG was removed by dialysis versus 5 L de-ionized water using cellulose membrane tubing with pore sizes of 50 kDa. The sample was left in dialysis over night at room temperature. This step was repeated 5 times. Finally, the nanocubes solution was concentrated by centrifugation in a centrifuge filter (molecular cut-off point 100 kDa) and analysed by FTIR, DLS, TEM and TGA.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). TGA measurements were carried out by using a TA instruments TGA Q500 thermal analyzer in the temperature range 25–500 °C with a heating rate of a 10 °C/min under N₂ flow (100 mL/min). TGA samples were prepared by placing a sample aliquot onto the pan, and heating at 110 °C in order to evaporate the water (equilibration time was 30 min).

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR). Spectra were recorded with a Bruker vertex 70v Fourier transform infrared spectrometer.

Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS). DLS characterization was performed on a Zetasizer Nano ZS90 (Malvern, USA) equipped with a 4.0 mW He-Ne laser, operating at 633 nm, and an Avalanche photodiode detector. Measurements were made at 25°C.

High and Low Resolution Transmission Electron Microscopy (HRTEM). High Resolution TEM (HRTEM) observations were performed with a JEOL JEM-2200FS microscope equipped with a field emission gun working at 200 kV, a CEOS spherical aberration corrector of the objective lens allowing for a spatial resolution of 1 Å, and an in-column Omega energy filter. The samples were prepared by drop-casting concentrated NC solutions on ultrathin carbon-coated 400 mesh copper grids. After the deposition the TEM samples were left few hours in a pumping station letting the solvent evaporate before the HRTEM imaging. HRTEM analysis displayed iron oxides nanocubes with the typical {100} crystal shape of perfect cubes and exhibited lattice parameters consistent with spinel ferrite phase (Figure S8). Low resolution TEM measurements were performed with a JEOL JEM 1011 microscope operating at 100 kV accelerating voltage.

High Resolution Scanning Electron Microscopy (HRSEM). High Resolution Scanning Electron Microscopy (HRSEM) analysis of selected samples was carried out using a JEOL JSM 7500FA, equipped

with a cold field emission gun (single crystal tungsten <310> emitter, ultimate resolution of 1nm) and operating at 15 kV in secondary electron (SE) imaging mode. A drop of the sample suspension (5 μ L) was deposited on a highly polished <111> silicon wafer substrate (0,5mm x 0,5mm).

Elemental Analysis. The elemental analysis of the samples was performed by digesting a few microliters of each sample in 2.5 ml of aqua regia and later diluting to a known volume with miliQ water. The measurement was performed with the iCap 6000 Series Induced Coupled Plasma - Atomic Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-AES) instrument from Thermo Fisher.

Magnetic measurements. Magnetic characterization was carried out by using a superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID) from Quantum Design. Magnetization curves were measured from -80 to 80 kOe at 5 K and 298 K upon zero field cooling (ZFC). Zero field cool (ZFC) and field cool (FC) curves were recorded to measure the thermal dependence of the magnetization. To determine the magnetization per unit mass (emu/g), the net magnetic moment of the suspension was normalized by the total mass particles, determined from the mass of iron (quantified by ICP-AES). Due to the experimental error associated to the measurement of the iron content, saturation magnetization values can show a deviation of about a 10% from its real value.

Hyperthermia measurements. For the hyperthermia characterization a commercially available set up was used (DM100 Series, nanoScale Biomagnetics Corp.). To evaluate the SAR of the IONPs, 700 μ l of water soluble IONC solution was introduced into a sample holder isolated from the system by a vacuum chamber in order to perform the measurements under close-to-adiabatic conditions. To minimize the error on the SAR, the concentration of the solution was set between 4 and 5 g/L in iron. The device is capable to generate AC magnetic field in the different frequencies (109 kHz, 220 kHz and 300 kHz) with magnetic field amplitudes up to 32 kAm⁻¹. In this regard the major technical limitation of the device is represented by a restriction on the magnetic field amplitude for some of the frequencies, being 32 kAm⁻¹ the highest amplitude reached only for 109 kHz. All measurements, if not otherwise stated, were performed in water ($C_{\text{water}} = 4185 \text{ J L}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$) and normalized by using the amount of iron evaluated by elemental analysis (g_{Fe}/L). All reported SAR values and error bars were calculated from the mean and standard deviation

respectively of at least four experimental measurements and were calculated according to the following equation:

$$\text{SAR(W/g)} = C/m \cdot dT/dt \quad (\text{eq. 1})$$

where C is the specific heat capacity of water per unit volume and m is the concentration (g/L of Fe) of magnetic material in solution. The measurements were carried out in close-to-adiabatic conditions, thus the slope of the curve dT/dt was measured by taking into account only the first few seconds.

Results and Discussion

Synthesis. A typical synthesis of cubic shaped IONPs reported earlier by us in a previous work consisted of the following steps:⁴ first, iron (III) acetylacetonate, decanoic acid and DBE were mixed together. After the solution was degassed at 65°C for 120 minutes, it was first heated up to 200 °C under a nitrogen blanket and then kept at this temperature for 2 hours. After that, the temperature was further increased, at various heating rates, up to reflux (about 290-295 °C). The reaction was then left under reflux for 1 hour. By monitoring the reaction temperature over time we noticed that, soon after the mixture had reached refluxing conditions, the temperature started to drop from 295°C to 260-270°C accompanied by random temperature dips of up to 20 degrees (see Figure 1A, red dashed line).

We correlated the slow temperature decay and the fast dips to the decomposition of DBE. Indeed, it was previously reported that DBE decomposes between 310 °C and 350 °C.³² Also, the decomposition temperature can drop significantly in the presence of an acid.³² So, it is reasonable to assume that DBE started decomposing already below 300°C due to the presence of decanoic acid and/or iron (III) acetylacetonate. The two molecules deriving from the decomposition of the DBE (toluene and benzaldehyde, in equal amounts),³² have much lower boiling points (110 °C and 178 °C) compared to the reflux temperature and therefore their presence in solution can be identified as the main cause of the temperature instability in the synthesis. Repeating this protocol at apparently the same experimental conditions yielded varying results in terms of nanocrystal sizes and size distributions, suggesting that such temperature instabilities are most likely the cause of the lack of reproducibility. In order to stabilize the

temperature, another solvent with higher boiling point is needed. Our choice fell on squalane as it can be considered inert under the present reaction conditions, and additionally it has a high boiling point (456°C at 760 mmHg). For example, the temperature profile of a synthesis carried out with a mixture of 18 mL DBE and 7 mL squalane was much smoother than that of the same reaction carried out in DBE only, *i.e.* with no temperature dips (see Figure 1A, black line). With the addition of squalane, repeated syntheses at the same conditions yielded IONPs with reproducible size and shape distributions. A detailed description of the syntheses procedures is reported in the ESI.

Figure 1. (A) Temperature profile at the refluxing stage for a typical synthesis of iron oxide nanocubes obtained by mixing 1 mmol of iron (III) acetylacetonate and 4.5 mmols of decanoic acid with 25 mL of DBE (red dashed line) or a mixture of 18 mL of DBE and 7 mL of squalane (black line); (B) Nanocrystal

size evolution as a function of the volumes of DBE and squalane. The total volume of the solution per synthesis was fixed to 25 mL. Electron micrographs of the color coded samples are reported in Figure 2.

The volume ratio between DBE and squalane had a strong influence over both the final size and shape of the particles: by increasing the volume fraction of squalane over that of DBE (and keeping the other parameters constant), larger particles, with sizes up to 100 nm, could be synthesized. This is shown in Figure 1B (see also Figure S1). At the same time, the shape evolved from cubic, for the smaller particles (Figure 2 A-B), to truncated octahedra (Figure 2C) and then to octahedra for the larger particles (Figure 2D, see also Figure S1 of the ESI). Notice that the refluxing temperature reached by the reaction system depended on the relative ratio of the solvents: the addition of the squalane shifted this temperature from *ca.* 290°C (when only DBE was used) up to 310 °C, when only squalane was used. In the latter case, mixtures of octahedral and irregularly shaped particles, of about 81 ± 15 nm average size, were formed (see Figure S2A).

It is interesting to note that Kim *et al.*, in order to synthesize regular and monodisperse 22 nm iron oxide nanocubes, added 4-biphenylcarboxylic acid to DBE, following a protocol similar to the one discussed here.²⁹ While the role of this compound in that work was that of a surfactant, its boiling point of 373 °C suggests that an additional role was likewise that of stabilization of the synthesis temperature. DBE or perhaps its decomposition products appear to act as essential shape directing agents, as reported both by us and by Kim *et al.* in previous works.²⁸⁻²⁹ Our data suggest additionally a role on regulating the size of the particles, because the more DBE was added, the smaller the particles were (see ESI). Because indeed DBE is decomposing in the reaction environment, we decided to study the effect of the by-products of the thermal decomposition³² by deliberately introducing them as pure chemicals in the synthesis.

Figure 2. Representative scanning and transmission (inset) electron microscopy images of iron oxide nanocubes synthesized by tuning the relative amount of squalane. The total volume of solution was equal to 25 mL in all syntheses and the volume ratio between DBE and squalane was: 23:2 (A), 7:18 (B), 4:21 (C) and 3:22 (D). These conditions lead to nanocrystals sizes equal to: 14 ± 2 nm (A), 26 ± 2 nm (B), 38 ± 4 nm (C) and 100 ± 7 nm (D). Scale bars correspond to 100 nm both in the TEM and in the SEM images. The color coded images are obtained at the corresponding solvent conditions highlighted with the same color code in Figure 1B.

We excluded a possible role of toluene due to its comparatively low boiling point and poor coordinating ability. We were also able to exclude any significant effect of benzyl alcohol, another possible side product of the thermal decomposition of DBE, in regulating the size and shape of the particles *via* a series of control experiments (see Figure S3). Positive results were obtained instead with benzaldehyde. In these latter experiments, due to the still low boiling point of benzaldehyde, we preferred first to prepare and degas a solution containing only squalane, iron (III) acetylacetonate and decanoic acid, and then inject

benzaldehyde. After following the heat up steps described in the ESI, cubic shape nanocrystals were obtained. Moreover, by increasing the amount of benzaldehyde, the size of the particles decreased while their shape remained cubic (Figure S2). These experiments therefore suggest that benzaldehyde, one of the decomposition products of DBE, is both a size and shape regulating agent. Size regulation might be as result of an interaction/synergy between benzaldehyde and the iron decanoate complex increasing the nucleation rate. The effect on shape is less obvious and will deserve further scrutiny. As a note, when the concentration of benzaldehyde exceeded 0.9 M, the size distribution broadened and the particles had a variety of shapes.

Overall, in our syntheses the relative amount of the two solvents allows for coarse tuning of the size and of the shape from cubic particles in the range from 14 to 35 nm, and to the truncated octahedral or octahedral for sizes above 40 nm. Once the solvent conditions were set, such that a rough control over the nanoparticle size was achieved, the size of the IONPs could be further fine-tuned by two additional parameters: the heating rate and the iron (III) acetylacetonate to decanoic acid ratio. For example, when working with a DBE:squalane ratio of 1.5:1, a decrease in the heating rate from 7 °C/min to 1.6 °C/min led to an increase in the final particle size from 22 nm to 33 nm (Figure 3). Based on previously reported results, we speculate that a low heating rate likely promotes nucleation already at lower temperatures.²⁸ But then, only a few seeds will be formed and they will prevent further nucleation at high temperatures by quickly consuming monomers and evolving into larger nanoparticles. A similar trend was observed when the ratio of iron (III) acetylacetonate to decanoic acid was varied: a decrease in that ratio led to a decrease in particle size. This is likely ascribed to the presence of an excess of decanoic acid which could better stabilize the initial clusters, thus promoting the nucleation (more initial seeds consume more iron precursor and thus less iron is left in solution for further growth of the seeds resulting in smaller nanoparticles) (Table S1 and Figure S4).²⁷ Thus both parameters independently play an important role on the synthesis, and indeed we could successfully exploit them to finely tune the final nanoparticle size.

Figure 3. Effect of the heating ramp (from 200°C up to reflux) on the size of the iron oxide nanocubes. When this rate was reduced from 7 °C/min to 2.5 °C and 1.6 °C/min (A), the size of the particles increased from 22 ± 2 nm (B) to 28 ± 3 nm (C) and then to 31 ± 3 nm (D), respectively. All these syntheses were run in a mixture of 15 mL of DBE and 10 mL of squalane and at a fixed iron (III) acetylacetonate to decanoic acid ratio of 1:4.

Water transfer. After nucleation and growth, the nanocrystals were stable only in organic media and further processing was required to transfer them into water. For cube shaped IONPs larger than 25nm, the magnetic inter-particle interactions at room temperature are strong enough to hamper *ex situ* coating protocols of single crystal with amphiphilic shells or ligands.³¹ In these procedures, the colloidal stability of the as-synthesized IONPs is crucial since strong attractive inter-particles forces would preclude the water transfer of nanocubes as individually coated and non-agglomerated particles.¹³ This is not a trivial issue as hitherto it is not clear how aggregation can affect the final SAR values for IONPs.^{13, 33} Indeed in a previous work⁴ we demonstrated already that for a successful polymer coating of individual IONPs high dilutions and increased temperatures are necessary. However, with this protocol only nanocrystals with sizes up to 25 nm could be transferred to water as single crystals, while larger particles were transferred as small clusters.⁴ This is an intrinsic limit of the polymer coating procedure as it imposes a solvent evaporation step in which both the nanoparticles and the polymer are gradually concentrated until the solvent is completely removed. Our results were also confirmed by Bae *et al.*,¹³ who took advantage of

the polymer coating procedure to transfer, as small aggregates of multiple nanocubes (4 to 6 nanocubes per cluster), 30 nm nanocubes by using a dopamine modified dextran polymer and study their heat performance.¹³

To overcome the limitations of the polymer coating procedure, we have developed an *in situ* ligand exchange protocol at elevated temperatures. Since magnetic inter-particle interactions are temperature dependent and stronger at lower temperatures, we intentionally injected amphiphilic GA-PEG, acting as surfactants, directly to the reaction flask after reducing the temperature of the reaction mixture from reflux down to 70° C. GA-PEG represents a suitable ligand for the nanocubes: it bears a gallol group that strongly coordinates the iron oxide surface, while the PEG chain introduces steric hindrance that stabilizes the nanoparticles in water.³⁴⁻³⁵ Successful *in situ* ligand exchange was achieved by addition of a large excess of GA-PEG molecules (1.5 mmol GA-PEG to 1mmol Fe precursor) and a base (1mL triethylamine), which deprotonates the hydroxyl groups of the gallol unit and increases its binding tendency towards the IONPs surface. After overnight stirring under N₂ atmosphere at 70°C, the PEGylated particles could be transferred almost quantitatively to water by phase extraction from the hydrophobic crude reaction solution that contained the particles, reaction solvents and eventually unreacted Fe precursors (Figure 4A and the ESI for the detail protocol). To this end, the crude solution was added to a 500 mL separating funnel containing water. The mixture was emulsified by shaking and the PEGylated particles almost immediately entered the aqueous phase after phase mixing and segregation. After extensive sample cleaning from unbound GA-PEG molecules by dialysis against milliQ water, the samples were analysed by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), dynamic light scattering (DLS) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) (see Figure 4 and Figure S6). The good match between the FTIR signals of GA-PEG and the extracted PEGylated particles (Figure 4C) confirmed the presence of GA-PEG on the particle surface which was found to contribute by 13 w% to the total mass of the nanoparticles that corresponds by a rough estimation of about 3000PEG molecules for nanocube (see TGA of Figure S6). DLS results of PEGylated particles (Figure 4D and table S3, of the ESI) were indicative of narrow size distributions and absence of aggregated particles for the entire size series.

We want to underline that the present *in situ* exchange protocol is particularly suitable for large and strongly interacting particles, which so far were never obtained as single water-soluble crystals and thus demonstrates the advantage of the *in situ* procedure over traditional post-synthesis exchange protocols. In a typical post synthesis ligand exchange protocol,³⁶ stabilization in water was shown to be unproblematic for nanoparticles with edge diameters up to 25 nm, but partial agglomeration was found to negatively affect the colloidal stability of larger nanoparticles (data not shown). On the contrary, the approach presented here allows for water transfer of larger iron oxide nanocubes (which exhibit strong magnetic interactions) with yields usually above 70% for IONPs of up to 35 nm and up to 90% for smaller nanocubes.

Figure 4. A) Scheme of the one-pot approach for the water transfer of iron oxide nanocubes. Amphiphilic GA-PEG molecules (dissolved in chloroform) are injected together with triethylamine after allowing the reaction solution to cool down from 300°C to 70°C in N₂ atmosphere. After overnight reaction, the PEGylated particles could be transferred from the organic phase by extraction with water. B) Representative TEM image of properly cleaned PEGylated particles in water. C) FTIR spectra of GA-PEG and IONPs@GA-PEG. The good match between the signals for C-H stretching (at ca. 2900 cm⁻¹),

the C-O stretching (ca. 1095 cm^{-1}) and the fingerprints of PEG at 943 and 833 cm^{-1} confirm the successful PEGylation of the nanocrystals. D) Hydrodynamic radii in number % measured by DLS for particles with cube edges of $35 \pm 2\text{ nm}$, $24 \pm 2\text{ nm}$, $19 \pm 2\text{ nm}$ and $14 \pm 1.5\text{ nm}$. Hydrodynamic sizes, estimated by DLS, are in good agreement with the sizes and size distributions measured by TEM.

Hyperthermia measurements. The heat performance of IONPs was measured in water. SAR values, expressed as W/g_{Fe} were calculated by measuring the initial slope of the temperature vs. time curve and upon normalization to the iron amount considering the heat capacity of water (see ESI). Four samples with cube edge of $14 \pm 1.5\text{ nm}$, $19 \pm 2\text{ nm}$, $24 \pm 2\text{ nm}$ and $35 \pm 2\text{ nm}$ (Figure S7) were prepared and their SAR were measured at different oscillating magnetic field amplitudes (12 kAm^{-1} , 16 kAm^{-1} , 20 kAm^{-1} , 24 kAm^{-1} and 32 kAm^{-1}) and at three different frequencies (109 kHz , 220 kHz and 300 kHz).

The resulting SAR values as a function of the applied magnetic field amplitudes at different frequencies for IONPs of different sizes are displayed in Figure 5. Several interesting trends can be observed: at low applied magnetic field amplitudes, 19 nm and 24 nm particles exhibited higher SAR values than the 35 nm particles at all the frequencies tested. However, the trend was reversed above a field amplitude of $20\text{--}24\text{ kAm}^{-1}$, where the SAR value for 35 nm IONPs increased. At 300 kHz , the 35 nm sample exhibited the highest SAR values among the four samples tested ($1391\text{ W/g}_{\text{Fe}}$ at 320 kHz and 24 kAm^{-1}). Interestingly, despite the 19 nm and 24 nm particles exhibited high SAR values, their heating performance appeared to saturate when the field was increased from 20 to 24 kAm^{-1} (Figure 5 and S11). On the other hand, 35 nm IONPs showed a sudden increase when the magnetic applied field overcame a certain value (18 kAm^{-1}) at high frequencies (300 kHz and 220 kHz).

Figure 5. SAR values as a function of the magnetic applied field at A) 109 kHz, B) 220 kHz and C) 300 kHz, for iron oxide nanocubes of $14 \pm 1.5 \text{ nm}$ (black squares ■), $19 \pm 2 \text{ nm}$ (red triangles ▲), $24 \pm 2 \text{ nm}$ (blue circles ●) and $35 \pm 2 \text{ nm}$ (green rhombi ◆). Each experimental data point was calculated as the mean value of at least 4 measurements and error bars indicate the standard deviation.

So far, for iron oxide cubes with sizes of 35 nm, the reported SAR values in the literature were always lower than those measured on the sample studied here.⁴ In general, the data reported on particles larger

than 25 nm were referred to aggregates, which might be the reason for a lower heat performance.⁴ Our results instead indicate that non-aggregated cubic shaped IONPs of 35 nm, above a certain magnetic field amplitude, have higher SAR performance than the 19 and 24 nm nanocubes. This difference in the SAR trends recorded between the 19 and 24 nm and the 35 nm nanocubes might be assigned to the differences in their magnetic properties: in the range between 20 and 35 nm the transition from superparamagnetic to ferromagnetic single domain nanocrystals at room temperature seems to take place (Figure S10). Also, our data on the 35 nm nanocubes fit nicely with the observations on magnetosomes, in which cube shaped IONPs of about 45 nm exhibit outstanding SAR values.^{37 12}

It is also worthy to mention that, for 19 nm cube shaped IONPs, the SAR values measured by us are in good agreement with our recently reported values for cube shaped particles synthesized by standard methods and transferred in water as single crystals *via* a polymer coating approach (within a deviation of about 10 %).⁴ This means that the procedure reported here to synthesize and transfer the particles in water does not alter the magnetic properties of the particles with respect to our previous approach, further corroborated by both structural analysis and magnetic characterization (Figure S8, S9, S10 and Table S2).

The evolution of the SAR as a function of the magnetic applied field of cube shaped IONPs was somehow different from that predicted by the linear response theory.⁶⁻⁷ While the here reported SAR values increase linearly with the frequency (Figure S11), as predicted by the linear response theory, their evolution as a function of the applied magnetic field (Figure 5) does not follow the expected square dependence ($SAR \propto H^2$).⁷ Instead, our data clearly indicate that, for 19 and 24 nm cubes, the SAR values saturate above a certain applied magnetic field. Because the linear response theory does not take into account hysteresis losses and our data do not properly follow the trend, we conclude that hysteresis losses might be the main heating mechanism involved here, in agreement with a recently reported study in which the same heating mechanism was recalled.³⁸

Finally, when SAR values are plotted as a function of the Hf factor (see Figure S13), it can be observed that most of our experimental data are below the limit that is considered biologically safe ($Hf = 5 \cdot 10^9$ kAs⁻¹m⁻¹)²⁴ whit values between 400 W/g_{Fe} and 800 W/g_{Fe}.²⁸ These values confirm that iron oxide

nanocubes are excellent heat mediators for hyperthermia treatment, and that the 35 nm nanocubes are promising candidates too.

Conclusions

To summarize, monodisperse water soluble iron oxide nanocrystals with a well-defined cubic (14 to 35 nm) or octahedral (40 to 100 nm) shape were synthesized following a novel approach in which a binary solvent mixture was the key to control the size and size dispersion. The relative ratio of squalane/DBE helped to tune the gross size of the nanocrystals. The decomposition products of DBE seemed to be crucial to synthesize cubic shaped nanoparticles with control over the size and shape. For fine-tuning of the size, the heating rate as well as the ratio of decanoic acid to iron (III) acetylacetonate can then be exploited. The combination of these parameters allowed us to synthesize nearly monodisperse nanocubes over a broad range of sizes with high reproducibility. Finally, the *in situ* ligand exchange by using a GA-PEG molecule provides well dispersed single crystals with diameters up to 35 nm. Outstanding SAR values were recorded for the 19 and 24 nm nanocube, as well as for the 35 nm nanocubes, in all cases coated as single crystals. In this regard, the 35 nm cubes, transferred into water as individually coated particles, exhibited the highest SAR values (up to 1400 W/g_{Fe}) among the tested samples. This is a remarkable result, not reported to date, because no procedures were available to transfer large nanoparticles (above 25 nm) as individual particles. Moreover, it is in agreement with what has been observed for magnetosomes in which high SAR values were measured for 45 nm IONPs.³⁷

With the procedure here developed being a thermal decomposition method, we can produce per each synthesis 30 up to 70 mg of water soluble nanocube sample with very high control over the size and shape. This yield however is significantly different than the one obtained by gram scale approach like for instance co-precipitation methods.³⁹ In view of their medical application, much effort should be undertaken to scale up these protocols. Nevertheless, the high SAR values measured of those water soluble nanoparticles together with the high control over the size and shape at a scale below 35 nm will allow to obtain injectable

nano-heaters at a high heat efficiency and at low dose of nanocubes, thus eventually maximizing therapeutic effects while minimizing side effects. These materials deserve further *in vivo* investigations.

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SYNOPSIS TOC (Word Style “SN_Synopsis_TOC”).

One pot synthesis of monodisperse water soluble iron oxide nano-crystals with high values of specific absorption rate

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